

Transnational & Virtual Access in Horizon Europe SERV Projects

Transnational and Virtual Access to Research Infrastructure
Services under Horizon Europe INFRA-SERV Projects:
Stakeholder Experiences and Policy Feedback

Brussels, 30-01-2025

Workshop report

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1. Context, objectives and conduct of the workshop

Transnational Access (TNA) to Research Infrastructures (RI) is the core activity of Horizon Europe (HE) SERV projects, and a large fraction of EU funding under the HE Research Infrastructures Programme is expected to support the latter. With 23 SERV projects now underway, it was time to gather SERV project coordinators, TNA programme managers, and relevant stakeholders such as ESFRI representatives and RI National Contact Points (NCP), for a one-day workshop, to share their experience, discuss any issues encountered and exchange wider views on TNA delivery under HE SERV projects.

Prior to the workshop, REA conducted a survey amongst all 23 SERV projects, asking for feedback on key aspects of TNA to be addressed. A presentation of the survey results opened the workshop.

To illustrate divergent modes of TNA implementation, coordinators from selected SERV projects presented their projects focussing on key features of TNA, such as the percentage of the total budget spent on TNA, reimbursement models, transnational vs virtual access, consortium architecture for TNA delivery, thematic fields, and challenge-driven vs curiosity-driven SERV.

Thereafter, REA and Commission staff moderated four discussion sessions:

- Session 1: TNA at the core of SERV projects
- Session 2: Administrative challenges and complexity of TNA
- Session 3: Sustainability of TNA
- Session 4: Impact of SERV projects on policies and innovation

Key aspects of the respective session topics were discussed and the comprehensive notes taken on the many contributions received, form the basis of this report.

Annexed to this report are the Agenda (Annex 1), the Participants list (Annex 2) and the Acronyms list (Annex 3). All the presentations are publicly available on CIRCABC group 'REA Horizon Europe Research infrastructures', in [TNA workshop 2025](#).

2. Executive Summary

The following summarises the four discussion sessions' key messages.

2.1. TNA at the core of SERV projects (Session 1)

- Dedicating above 60% of a SERV project's total EU contribution to TNA (TNA-linked travel costs left aside) is seen as difficult, due to the high additional absolute costs linked to TNA user projects (purchase contracts, VAT issues, staff & user management). These additional costs are not completely covered by EU reimbursement. EU-funds are used to cover TNA associated user travel costs, which in several cases is considered essential. This adds to the budget portion contributing to TNA.
- SERV projects' training measures targeting potential TNA users, Joint Research Activities (JRA) to upgrade or expand support services and work towards making TNA more sustainable, should continue to be supported - at least to a moderate extent-, as incentives to maintain TNA and keep SERV projects attractive.

- Coordination/networking/administration activities inherent to the current cluster nature of SERV projects are overly complex. Mechanisms are needed to develop and spread guidance documents and best practices. This could simplify administration and free up more budget to support TNA.
- Centralising and harmonising TNA management and delivery modes within and across several SERV projects, would reduce management costs and allow to balance TNA demand and available budget. However, it would put more responsibility on Project Coordinators or other TNA delivery hubs in the project.
- Longer duration/larger financial volume of SERV projects would make the efforts to set up TNA more cost efficient and would provide longer term perspectives for researchers who depend on TNA (e.g. from Widening Countries).

2.2. TNA Administrative challenges and complexity (Session 2)

- A coherent and hierarchically structured RI terminology is needed. The currently used terminology is found to be vaguely defined and sometimes discretionarily applied, leading to confusion. There is a need for a simplified, standardised, clearly communicated, and uniformly applied terminology.
- Participants perceive TNA schemes as very complex. There is an overall need to simplify SERV projects, in particular regarding TNA management, delivery and reimbursement procedures.
- While the flexibility of three TNA reimbursement models (actual cost, unit cost, and combined cost) is still considered useful by most participants, some suggest that the combined model may not be needed.
- The high administrative burden of managing SERV projects needs to be decreased. Demand-driven, dynamic SERV projects currently require too many amendments. Not having clearly tagged cost categories for TNA causes issues in terms of unclear budgeting of TNA, etc.
- Clearer instructions on TNA reporting should be given and be implemented in a harmonised way across projects; reporting requirements should be simple and coherent.
- Harmonised, clearly communicated TNA management procedures would facilitate managing SERV projects.
- Managing TNA more centrally, e.g. using a central TNA platform, would simplify TNA delivery. This would also allow to balance divergent demands for RI installations, and to more strategically spread TNA across provider sites. However, such more central TNA budget management would put greater responsibility on respective hub entities.
- Handling of TNA user travel reimbursement varies significantly between SERV projects, being in some cases even at the discretion of individual PIs. More unified rules are needed, such that travel allowances and their amounts are decided upon more selectively (i.e. given only when really needed), more transparently and in a harmonised way. This may be better achievable if TNA user travel reimbursement is managed centrally within a SERV project.
- Lump sum reimbursement of SERV projects would alleviate the administrative burden of financial reporting. However, the upfront distribution of the TNA budget among partners might conflict with the dynamic and needs-driven feature of SERV

projects, unless the TNA budget is centrally held/managed by one or few TNA managing hubs.

- Online resources offered as VA can be complementary to TNA, but it needs to be clarified what VA reimbursement comprises. For instance, whether development and maintenance of an online data resource qualifies as costs linked to VA-use, or if such resource development should rather be addressed through respective TECH calls.
- Setting up *de-novo* data resources for VA specifically for a given SERV project may lead to undesirable redundancies with existing common data repositories that should ideally be use instead.

2.3. TNA Sustainability (Session 3)

- The concept at the base of the EU Research Infrastructures programmes is understood and shared: while building and maintaining research infrastructures remain under national remit, creating an EU-level 'umbrella' RI - composed of such nationally funded RI facilities - has been supported by EU funds such as the INFRA DEV calls (in some cases, EU structural funds given to Member States (MS) did serve to build infrastructure capacities as such, which should be explored further).
- By contrast, the Transnational Access (TNA) of researchers to nationally or at EU-level jointly, managed RI facilities, requires sustained EU funding. Options for long-term TNA and VA delivery include (i) longer duration of SERV projects, (ii) more central roles for stable EU-level RIs in TNA management, or (iii) EOSC-like (co-fund) partnerships, or (iv) still more centralised TNA support management by one, or few, mandated EU-level bodies.
- RIs participate in EU research projects under the HE Pillar II Clusters, but only in few thematic areas. Targeted efforts and mechanisms should facilitate this integration, e.g. references to RIs in Pillar II Cluster topics, mechanisms to avoid risk of double funding, etc.
- Exploring mechanisms of national co-funding via the HE Co-Fund Partnership tool is perceived as realistic. However, to be attractive, the percentage of the EU contribution for joint EU & MS TNA calls should be above 30%.
- New partnership models are conceivable whereby EU and MS would jointly set up RIs with an ex-ante agreement on a fixed % obligation to provide free-of-charge TNA to users across EU.
- While industry revenues are frequent for national RIs, this is not a realistic option for supporting sustainable EU-level TNA use: support by publicly funded RIs to industry causes issues for both sides, e.g. Open Science obligations to publish results, prohibition to subsidise industries, and so on.
- A planned Coordination and support actions (CSA) topic under the Research Infrastructures Work Programme 2025 should give the RI community an opportunity to develop and suggest concepts for longer-term sustained TNA access schemes.

2.4. SERV projects' impact on policies & innovation (Session 4)

- Clearer guidance is needed on reporting on impact generated by SERV projects, and in particular from TNA user projects.
- A central TNA access portal managed across SERV projects would be useful also for outcome and impact reporting.
- SERV projects provide data evidence and coordination/harmonisation efforts to support EU policies, the Joint Research Centre (JRC) and EU Agencies in their mandates (including EU regulatory actions), as well as challenge driven HE Missions and Partnerships.
- Conversely, in some cases, policy stakeholders (such as EU Agencies, the JRC, Partnerships, etc.) contributed to shaping TNA calls to better align SERV projects' outcomes with the need to support EU policies or identified societal challenges.
- International collaboration is implicit for large RIs. Nevertheless, specific calls under the research infrastructure work programme requesting collaboration with identified non-EU target regions or countries according to EU international policy objectives are still needed (e.g., topics to enhance collaboration with Ukraine).
- Global research challenges, such as Covid, by nature require global cooperation, including collaboration between RIs.
- A collaboration framework and rules are needed to ensure reciprocity in collaborations with Third Countries (in particular with entities based in well-resourced partner countries), but also to restrict collaborations contrary to EU international policy objectives.
- Tracking the impact of SERV projects is challenging, especially the indirect impact derived from TNA projects as it peaks after the end of the project. Hence more guidance on how to follow-up after the end of projects is needed.
- Under SERV projects, RIs are only scarcely used by industry, though European industry indirectly benefits from cooperations with the academic researchers supported through TNA projects.
- A controversial debate arose on the formation of potential 'access bubbles' around existing 'excellence' communities. It was discussed whether too much focus on the excellence criterion for selection of TNA user projects may need to be complemented by incentives to explicitly support new users, thus truly addressing different criteria as defined by respective call topics.

3. Workshop Proceedings

3.1. Welcome, Introduction, Objectives

Sari Vartiainen-Mathieu (REA, Head of Unit for Reforming European R&I and European Research Infrastructures) opened by explaining the context and objectives of the workshop. With the externalisation of the HE Research Infrastructures programme to REA, the need of urgent simplification of the programme became clear.

The workshop aimed to hear from SERV Project Coordinators and TNA programme managers of currently running HE SERV projects, which experiences were acquired and what could be improved for the future.

Agnès Robin, (EC, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), Head of Sector for Open Science and Research Infrastructures,) informed that DG RTD had undertaken several consultations on the state of the art of TNA. The outcome of these studies should allow to draw lessons for the future (ESFRI access drafting group, TNA access study, consultation of H2020 projects), with the aim to keep RIs well on the agenda for the FP10 planning.

Andrea Hutterer (REA, Head of Sector for RIs) chaired the workshop.

3.2. Results from survey on SERV projects and TNA

The workshop started with an overview of the survey outcomes presented by Antonio Ventura (REA, RIs).¹ Key findings were highlighted for the following topical discussion sessions, including:

- Unbalanced coverage of thematic areas: No projects exclusively dedicated to Data, Computing & Digital RI, and only very few on Energy or Social Sciences & Humanities.
- In most projects TNA provider entities have the status of full grant beneficiaries.
- More than half of projects provide TNA only, i.e. they do not provide Virtual Access (VA).
- Most projects consider allocating 60% of the total budget to TNA as achievable, some projects could allocate more.
- Basic terms lack universal clarity: such as 'Research Infrastructure', 'Installation', 'User Group' or 'User Project'.
- Report requirements are not universally clear, particularly regarding VA.
- For sustainability of TNA delivery, most projects see national contributions as a realistic option, only some mention revenues from commercial entities, and none reported accessing other EU programmes.

3.3. Three example projects presented on different dimensions relevant to TNA

The CanSERV project (slides by Manuela Pausan & Thomas Steger, BBMRI ERIC)² is a partially challenge-driven SERV project (focus on HE Cancer Mission) coordinated by the Biobanking and BioMolecular Resources Research Infrastructure ERIC (BBMRI ERIC).

A cascade architecture with TNA budget holding beneficiaries and distributed, purchased-in TNA providers is implemented, offering unit costs (uc), actual costs (ac) and combined costs reimbursed TNA, but no VA.

¹ [TNA survey results and analysis, Antonio VENTURA, TNA Workshop 2025.](#)

² [canSERV project - Providing Cutting Edge Cancer Research Services Across Europe, TNA Workshop 2025.](#)

Challenges included setting up a common TNA access management tool, *de-novo* development of contracts for external TNA providers, and managing cross-RIs/cross-community integrated RI services.

In addition, liquidity issues were encountered for the TNA holding nodes due to EU-payment mode that faces budget holder nodes with problem to (pre-) finance external TNA providers from own institutional core resources. Exploring new and alternative reporting and financing models for TNA services might be worthwhile.

EURO-LABS (slides by Adam Maj, IFJ PAN Kraków)³ is a curiosity-driven SERV project in the physics domain, coordinated by the Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN).

Most beneficiaries also serve as TNA provider entities (flat architecture), offering both TNA (primarily access to beam lines) and VA.

Addressing synergies between their three TNA requiring thematic communities (nuclear physics, accelerators, detector technologies) is challenging.

TNA is in very high demand, with only part of the full costs covered by EU funding.

Diversity among TNA providers is tolerated, e.g. in terms of TNA call success rates and user follow-up. Sustainability largely hinges on the next EU call offering again a communities-spanning relevant topics.

Infra4NextGen (slides by Rory Fitzgerald, ESS ERIC)⁴ is a challenge-driven SERV project in the social sciences field, coordinated by the European Social Survey ERIC (ESS ERIC).

The project has foreseen no TNA, and shows only a small VA budget, as use of social sciences data does not incur additional expenses as per use case.

However, Virtual Access to social science data resources requires support to prepare data use for Virtual Access.

The project directly impacts EU Youth Policy through data provision for relevant policy consultation/co-creation.

3.4. Presentations on available views on TNA: ESFRI, TNA study report, SERV community feedback

Elena Hoffert (Vice-Chair of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures – ESFRI) presented the ESFRI drafting group’s Report on Access to Research Infrastructures.⁵

The report responds to ERA action 8, referring to research infrastructures, and is based on surveys querying both RI stakeholders and the RIs themselves. As challenges for sustained TNA, the following were identified: legal aspects regarding IPR, data protection, liability; distributed RIs having issues with TNA cost reimbursement to TNA providing RIs (e.g. for their Third Party in-kind contributions); the general challenge to maintain TNA as EU funding is needed, but thus far depends on project support; lack of wider awareness of RIs and the TNA they offer.

³ [Infra4NextGen - Providing research infrastructure services to support Next Generation EU, TNA workshop 2025.](#)

⁴ [EURO-LABS – EUROpean Laboratories for Accelerator Based Science, TNA workshop 2025.](#)

⁵ [ESFRI Report on Access to Research Infrastructures, Elena Hoffert PPT, TNA Workshop 2025.](#)

The ESFRI group hence recommends a central platform for legal guidance related to TNA; exploring how different funding streams could support longer-term TNA; balancing curiosity- and challenge-driven TNA in EU-funded support; encouraging cooperation with SMEs and industries to enhance impact on innovation; and revising the Charter for Access to RIs to promote a 'priority-driven access' mode with respect to addressing societal/policy needs.

Audience reactions confirmed institutional financial/legal barriers for TNA, as mechanisms and scope of TNA and possible implications for national funding of RIs were not well understood. The RICH-Europe project referred to an already existing central TNA platform under the RICH-Europe project, but a comprehensive RI portal including a common platform for TNA access would go beyond.

A comment from the ERIC-Forum 2 project indicated that at least for ERICs, such a more comprehensive TNA platform already exists.

Contracted expert Audrey Richard on outcomes of commissioned TNA Access Study.⁶

EC/REA services had commissioned a TNA access study, conducted by Audrey Richard (COO and Deputy Director of the European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents - ERINHA) on TNA in H2020 IA and HE SERV projects. Key findings of those projects were presented by the contracted expert (also Coordinator of the ISIDORE SERV project).

The H2020 TNA containing IA projects were successful in terms of inclusivity of use of RI facilities, as in particular users from Widening Countries benefitted from access to RI installations across EU. In HE a trend was observed that larger EU level RIs (ESFRI, ERICs, International European Research Organisations-IERO) delivered a larger fraction of the access services, probably due to lifting earlier restrictions on these RIs with respect to offer EU-funded TNA. Gender imbalances persist, with more than 2/3 male RI users. Well beyond 90% of TNA users come from universities and research organisations. TNA data provided through EU services' tools were in general useful, except for sometimes unclear and inconsistent terms and reporting, in particular on TNA users and the output from user projects. Reporting on critical aspects e.g. underutilization of RI installations is not duly provided for, hence extracting negative information e.g. on gaps or redundancies is difficult. Follow-up with, and feedback from, TNA users after the end of project is done by only some SERV projects, hence longer-term impact of SERV projects is difficult to catch.

SERV community feedback from ReMade-at-ARI's TNA workshop: Barbara Schramm (Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf- HZDr) (see slides)⁷

Barbara Schramm reported on the outcomes of the TNA stakeholder brainstorming workshop, recently held by ReMade-at-ARI project (on Circular Economy) to explore with stakeholders perspectives for sustainability of TNA..

RIs, as a backbone of EU innovative research, play a role also in other EU programmes (e.g. ERC).

The European portfolio of RIs offering TNA is key for structuring the RI landscape in the European Research Area (ERA), as TNA pushes researchers beyond comfortable home zones and supports international and interdisciplinary collaboration, of particular interest for Widening Countries.

⁶ [TNA STUDY - Key Aspects of TNA Implementation, Audrey RICHARD, TNA Workshop 2025](#)

⁷ [TNA Report from a Brainstorming Meeting of stakeholders from the RI Access and TNA community, January 27-28, 2025, TNA workshop 2025.](#)

SMEs can benefit from EU-funded TNA as it de-risks innovation.

Improved service navigation and simplified access pathways would enhance TNA's reach, making RIs more visible and accessible. TNA requires additional effort, hence needs incentives for RIs to participate.

True costs of TNA need to be better compensated for. Sustained TNA funding including new co-funding models are vital for long-term TNA continuity, as well as smarter communication to raise more awareness with a still wider range of researchers using the RIs.

Transnationality and open data requirements constitute barriers for some players, in particular private. The diversity of the RI landscape, along with complicated access models, make it difficult for users to reach the most suitable resource for their needs.

Commonalities of RIs' governance, training measures and data handling could be exploited by having a central access platform with AI assistance to help users find the right RI; whether single-site, distributed, physical or virtual, could be capitalised by giving precise information and advice on respectively needed RI features. National regulations limit funding TNA solely through national budgets. Ensuring the long-term sustainability of TNA therefore requires a European funding commitment, which would then allow to explore co-funding models for TNA including also national resources.

Comments from audience ask to enable better findability of the various TNA offers by RIs. Others state that some projects do have such easy-to-find TNA platforms. Others point to EOSC as the natural starting point for findability of TNA; the EOSC framework should thus include a mandate to ensure RI findability and accessibility.

REA services state that to better assess the extent of transnational TNA use by SMEs, corresponding national benchmark figures are needed.

4. Compilation and aggregation of input received from workshop participants:

4.1. Session 1 TNA at core of SERV projects

How should we aim at a higher % of EU budget devoted to TNA?

Is the 'clustering of clusters' approach in SERV topics useful and can joint ESFRI/ERIC entities play an operational role for TNA management?

Views heard:

Allocating 50-60% of the total EU contribution to TNA is feasible. In addition to TNA, incentives such as training potential users as well as Joint Research Activities (JRA) to upgrade/expand support services and sustainability efforts are necessary to maintain TNA and keep the SERV cluster attractive.

Centralising TNA management through a Cascade Consortium architecture, which is already in place for some SERV projects, rather than a flat architecture could lead to efficiency gains. However, centralising TNA management increases the responsibility for central TNA managers (Coordinators, cluster hubs).

Centralising the TNA budget management via entities like ERICs might cause liquidity issues, as these EU-level 'umbrella' RI entities often lack enough resources to cover the full

TNA costs upfront. EU's pre-financing or interim payments do not completely cover the total costs of 'purchased-in' TNA.

Some consortia do not find TNA provision by many beneficiaries problematic, as it offers more flexibility for diverse TNA service. This approach also helps mitigate liquidity problems, as each TNA provider beneficiary may need to pre-finance TNA costs only as incurred by their institution.

More standardisation of TNA schemes and early guidance on implementation should be available at the start of projects. Templates for specific partner roles, such as 'purchasing' TNA service provision, could free up administrative and governance budgets, allowing for more TNA. A cross-project central platform or portal for sharing best practices would also be beneficial.

It was noted that smaller projects require a higher percentage of administrative effort to set up a new TNA project. Without adequate setup, the cost efficiency ratio of TNA-linked work versus administrative effort decreases.

Generally, the administrative requirements imposed by EU are too heavy: amendments for change of unit costs could be avoided by e.g. on-line adaption to changed CPI or changing energy costs.

Centralised TNA management could allow to 'level up' TNA delivery across provider partners, to balance between over- and undersubscribed RI sites/services. However, such balancing should not be managed by more EU-imposed rules but rather be left to consortia themselves. National RIs forming the physical infrastructure of an ERIC may not accept ERIC-managed central allocation of TNA to national ERIC members.

TNA costs are for many RIs only partially reimbursed by EU, and TNA providers thus need to ship in own resources.

Multi-partner ESFRI RIs such as ERICs as a central TNA provider, or having a standing capacity to operate TNA management, is seen by some as a means to save time and costs. While it may be beneficial for ESFRI RIs/ERICs to coordinate the operational side of TNA, this should not be made mandatory. In any case the 'most suitable' such ESFRI RI/ERIC should be found for such prominent role of operationally running TNA.

Setting up new governance and implementation structures with each SERV project is tedious and consumes administrative overhead. Longer project duration helps, along with provisions allowing to benefit from lessons learned and best practices. The central TNA management role may not be restricted to EU-level types of RIs, it could also be other e.g. international facilities or experienced national players.

More centralised, longer-term TNA management should not exclusively be done by ESFRI RIs or ERICs which would need incentives to assume such roles. Other appropriate RIs may also want to develop into these more central roles and should not be impeded.

With respect to centralising TNA management, consider separating evaluation of TNA user applications (that could still be done de-centrally at distributed TNA provider hubs) from centralised TNA budget management (e.g. shifts to respective partners to level use of different RI sites offering similar/same services).

A perceived programme tendency to support TNA in separation, rather than in conjunction with networking and service development as it is currently done, jeopardises additional benefits from networking (exchange of ideas and experiences, enhanced collaboration,

strategic input and alignment to EU priorities) and with Joint Research towards developing fit-for-future services at the cutting-edge of the respective domain.

4.2. Session 2 TNA Administrative Challenges and complexity

How can we address complexity of RI terminology?

How can TNA reimbursement models and VA be simplified?

Views heard:

The terms 'TNA' and 'access to RIs' can be misleading as they not only cover physical access to RI but also receiving RI services ('remote access') or access to data (as VA).

With respect to 'access', it should be clarified whether the term extends also to data sharing, or even just collaborations.

A clear and consistently communicated hierarchy of terms, from research infrastructures down to installations, services and units is needed as problems arise (e.g. for reporting) if terms are understood differently by partners, which results in communication problems for coordinators.

Guidance on use of terminology should be centrally available for TNA access provider entities and installations as well as for users. This guidance should comprise instructions for setting up access schemes and for creating well termed and interpreted TNA reporting sheets.

A list of definitions specified by EU could be added to the Charter for Access, making it a reference document for clarifying any questions regarding definitions of certain terms.

Additionally, a glossary of EU terminology used for RIs and TNA should be defined and translated into commonly used language.

Even experienced coordinators struggle to understand and apply the correct nomenclature. Clear descriptions of terms are needed, and synonyms should be avoided. Notably, the terms 'actual' and 'unit costs' reimbursement are not typically used in real world cost accounting, which instead relies on the concepts of direct and indirect costs are used. There is a clear need for an easily accessible glossary of terms related to TNA.

While the term 'Transnational Access' makes sense to some, others find the term 'RI services' useful; and some only find the use of the different reimbursement models for both TNA and VA adding to confusion.

Current cost models are conceptually useful, but standardisation of implementation of access methodology is needed, such that TNA models become auditable.

In particular large single-sited RIs' central accounting systems do not allow for separating specific TNA-linked costs from their other institutional costs. Also, how to account for Third Parties' in-kind personnel contributions when calculating uc-TNA costs, can cause problems.

The TNA actual costs model is considered more universally applicable, whereas unit costs are preferred mainly by RIs e.g. in the field of physics, that operate services with standardised time units of use of the large instrumentation, such as beamline hours.

The combined ac/uc reimbursement model could possibly be redundant by dissecting a combined model service into two complementary service components, that operate with different cost models.

Operating unit cost TNA may often entail a loss because historically fixed unit costs do not adjust for rising costs. In this context, the application of the ac-TNA model as part of a combined model can address dynamically changing cost items. The ac-TNA model will also be needed by e.g. smaller facilities that do not have a sufficient and constant number of users, and thus, lack the data needed to underpin the calculation of fixed unit costs.

The application of the unit cost model could be facilitated by allowing for flat rates (instead of historical real costs) for different cost categories as per country. This approach could be another way to calculate unit costs. Throughout the project's duration, allowable unit cost prices could be indexed e.g. according to inflation or be subject to regular updates based on the preceding years' costs. Such flexibility in applicable unit cost prices would reduce the need of amendments, potentially eliminating the necessity for the combined cost model.

COM services reply that currently provisions given in the Commission Decision authorising the use of unit costs for the costs of providing trans-national and virtual access in Research Infrastructures, have to be applied.⁸

The use of a lump-sum reimbursement approach applied for an entire SERV project would further remove the financial reporting burden; however, this would require centralised TNA distribution and preclude up-front distribution of fractions of TNA budget to individual project partners, as the eventual use of the partners' TNA provision is demand driven and cannot be exactly predicted at the time of lump sum budget distribution.

RIs are diverse and need the flexibility that the three TNA cost reimbursement models for RIs offer.

Reimbursement of TNA user travel costs overlaps with other EU support (REA services point to overlap with mobility support through the MSCA programme). However, in specific cases, travel reimbursement is needed to enable TNA (e.g. users travelling to remote RI locations, early career researchers, or those from Widening Countries, who are unlikely to receive travel funds from home institutions).

To a request to allow intra-consortium TNA use by users linked to project partners - in particular in cases where SERV consortia comprise almost all research actors in a given field - REA services respond that this is, in principle, already possible in GAs, but should not lead to a closed-shop scenario of internal TNA use.

Central TNA travel cost management across the SERV project could be entrusted to the coordinator, but that means more responsibility for Coordinators.

There could be a liquidity problem if the TNA budget is only partially prefinanced and kept centrally if with the coordinator.

TNA user-linked travel costs are always an element that requires actual cost reimbursement, as uc-TNA must not comprise user travel.

Reimbursement of TNA user travel often conflicts with national regulations that nationally funded institutions must follow for all travel cost reimbursements to either staff members or

⁸ [COMMISSION DECISION of 31.7.2024 amending Commission Decision C\(2021\)35 authorising the use of unit costs for travel, accommodation and subsistence costs under an action or work programme under the 2021-2027 multiannual financial framework.](#)

external TNA users. Therefore, unified European TNA travel reimbursement rules for SERV projects would be very useful.

Simplification of TNA schemes largely depends on EC/REA services, in particular through providing clearer guidance (e.g. on reporting) and more flexibility (e.g. amendments to update unit costs).

More centralised TNA budget management/distribution by coordinators or a few TNA hubs offers advantages, some already 'ringfence' all or part of the SERV TNA budget with the Coordinator or cluster hubs, to be released to partners according to demands/needs.

Streamlining EU's requirements regarding TNA reporting can mitigate administrative complexity, yet reporting on TNA remains key for the impact of SERV projects, and mitigating reporting obligations *vis-à-vis* EU means more responsibility for Coordinators/hub partners who centrally manage TNA budgets.

With actual cost TNA reporting, TNA related costs fall into different actual cost categories where they are not recognised anymore as being TNA related, but where they get mixed with same actual cost types incurred as provider's own costs for not TNA-related work; clean separate cost category is needed for covering all TNA linked actual costs.

REA services state that the general trust-based commission approach should also apply to TNA budget expenditure in a SERV project. Generally, trust-based approach should be used.

SERV project partners know best how to most efficaciously use and distribute TNA funds, in particular when managing the TNA budget centrally, e.g. by the Coordinator operating through a cascade funding architecture.

Simplifying SERV projects through lump sum reimbursements is currently unrealistic, as this would require distributing TNA funds to partners upfront without knowing how demand develops. This could impede the ability to allocate the TNA budget according to beneficiaries' actual TNA performance.

According to the survey conducted with SERV projects prior to the workshop, VA was used fewer than half of the SERV projects.

VA running in parallel to TNA is considered appropriate, as in some cases TNA generates the data subsequently utilised through VA services.

REA highlights the risk of double funding: if generation of data is reimbursed as TNA and then utilised as online VA without entailing additional use-case linked costs, this could lead to reimbursement twice

Maintaining data for VA incurs actual costs, including 'hidden costs' associated with maintaining databases, which can be linked to the number of uses of the resource. In some grant agreements no costs are assigned to VA.

Some argue against VA being an on-line used resource, as even TNA-derived new data should primarily be put in existing databases (with no extra costs linked to VA); instead of using specific VA provisions, EU should just impose on SERV partners and TNA users to give access to the data produced in context of the project.

Another point made on VA is that challenge-driven SERV projects, meant to support policy priorities, should not only populate the existing databases that are used to inform policy makers, but also develop the necessary tools that make relevant data, e.g., for HE missions,

easily findable. This would make infrastructures truly contributing to policy and societal challenges and HE missions.

Clarification is needed to discriminate between VA and remote TNA access. It is unclear what sort of actual costs can be linked to a VA use case, as VA does entail a lot of hidden costs (preparation, curation & archiving of data costs money) which cannot simply be presented as part of VA use cases.

EC services relate the history of shaping VA under HE: the intention was to simplify by removing use case-linked VA reimbursement and instead support only the development of online services. However, internal decisions resulted in introduction of the additional uc-VA option, which can actually lead to increased complexity.

ERIC-Forum project 2 conducted a survey among the ERICs: currently 68% of the ERICs offer virtual access, followed by physical (60%) and remote (56%) access, often combining these approaches. Virtual Access is predominantly free of charge and openly available, although for access to sensitive data user authentication is needed. EU funding is key for facilitating both Transnational and Virtual Access.

Developing data bases for VA falls under the remit of INFRATECH rather than INFRASERV projects. This speaks against charging or reimbursing costs for development of data resources through VA use cases.

A special case for VA could be VA services supported by openly available AI now, hence a new type of VA being AI driven data services.

4.3. Session 3 Sustainability of TNA

How can SERV RIs tap into other EU programmes/projects?

How can national funds be mobilised to make TNA sustainable?

Can commercial revenues generated by RIs contribute to sustaining TNA?

Views heard:

REA recalls the rationale of the EU's INFRA programme, namely that national RIs are funded by MS, while only their assembly under a new, joint, EU-level RI umbrella receives EU support (DEV calls). Sustaining EU-level umbrella RI entities is primarily done by MS' statutory contributions to e.g. ERICs. Activities of EU-level RIs/EU networks of RIs, in terms of TNA are fuelled by SERV projects (or H2020 IA). The main issue is the long-term sustainability of TNA.

This basic understanding is largely shared: SERV projects confirm that large RI facilities (e.g. polar vessels) are indeed supported by MS, while the transnational use of these vessels requires comparatively small amounts of money, but the challenge is to maintain this TNA in the longer term, i.e., beyond EU project support.

An exception is mentioned, namely that 'national' funds used for building RI can, in fact, be EU structural funds, in which case EU funds contribute to setting up RI facilities.

It must be clear that RIs' viability is ensured via other funds, then it remains the TNA access that requires EU support to ensure TNA in a consistent way in the longer term. RI maintenance does not require huge funding to maintain TNA operational.

One model from the field of HPC is that the EU co-funds, e.g., 50% of RI set-up/maintenance costs, so as to have a leverage on user access, such that initial EU support is conditional - that an agreed % of user access is provided later as free-of-charge transnational access for users across EU.

REA points to survey results indicating that none of the SERV projects reported tapping into other EU programmes, e.g., Cluster 2 research projects.

SERV projects report that preceding H2020 projects were heavily involved with EU cluster research projects, while current SERV projects are not yet ready.

A perceived risk of double funding can be addressed by devising proper mechanisms for cross-sources funding, e.g. with RIs/proxy beneficiaries of RI networks joining research projects with low or zero own initial budget, while, during the course of the project, other project beneficiaries needing RI services would then shift the respective shares of their own research budgets to the RIs. A further challenge lies at the level of eligibility of TNA cost categories (uc-TNA) under EU programmes other than the RI programme.

The European Commission should improve its awareness mechanism and communication about possible mechanisms; possibly, also the applicability of the uc-TNA COM Decision should be expanded to other programmes. An explicit reference to the desirable inclusion of RIs in research consortia should be made at the level of topic text, e.g., in HE Pillar II Cluster work programmes and calls.

Also, ensuring sustained EU support towards user travel & subsistence costs should be a mode to sustained EU support to TNA, at least for users' travel expenses.

EOSC has developed mechanisms to fund online RI services via a unique user's gate operation tool giving access to a catalogue of many EOSC-linked online services. It should be explored if this EOSC model can serve also as a functional model for the delivery of RIs' TNA services, while currently it serves for further development of the EOSC nodes, not to deliver research support to users as done in the context of TNA. In relation to VA access, EOSC may indeed help, but it is not the appropriate place to manage physical and remote TNA.

REA points to EOSC Partnership-like Joint Undertakings as a model where EU, MS and/or industry contribute funds; this could also be a framework for sustained TNA delivery.

In particular, distributed RIs/RI networks significantly rely on EU funds to reimburse costs of TNA access. The absence of such operational support could make RIs/RI networks disappear. The EC should decide, based on case-by-case assessments, if TNA operations of these RIs should be sustained; fixed EU- versus MS-budget shares should be established in advance to ensure continued national budget support (in essence a Public Partnership model).

REA focusses the discussion on the survey outcome that about half of the survey respondents consider national support towards TNA delivery possible.

Some large RIs provide co-funding anyway, as the EU reimbursement of TNA, in any case, covers only 20% of the full costs of each TNA use case; such rather moderate EU-contribution could/should be possible to sustain.

The co-funding scheme piloted with 2023 INFRA-SERV-01-03 was a good idea but should explicitly focus national co-funding on covering TNA, and not just report national RIs' institutional costs to be contributed as national co-funding.

100% EU support for transnational users' travel and subsistence to visit and use nationally maintained RIs (e.g., polar vessels) would already make EU-wide TNA use more sustainable.

To make co-funding of TNA by the EU attractive to Member States, it should go beyond only 30% EU contribution to joint calls with national funders in Co-Fund partnerships; rather, a 70% EU-contribution should be given to partnership calls, which could make a Co-Fund Action more successful in terms of getting also national funds used for TNA support (albeit only at, e.g., 30%).

The large heterogeneity of conditions for co-funding by MS' national sources entails a diversity of different national rules to be considered to fund external users from other countries using a largely nationally funded RI; hence, very different modes and incentives are needed to lure national funders into EU-wide TNA support. Apart from the diversity of applicable national rules, a recent survey also points to differing willingness of countries towards co-funding the transnational use of their RI facilities. A reasonable way to ensure some national co-funding to TNA use is at least partial national co-funding of travel costs of users from the respective sending country.

Specifically on the question if commercial revenues generated by RIs can contribute to sustaining TNA:

Only few of the SERV survey responses indicated revenues derived from industry use of TNA. The ensuing discussion focussed on how such revenues could possibly contribute towards the sustainability of TNA.

The ESFRI RIs' national RI members are well used by industry, but this does not benefit sustainability of TNA delivered by EU-level RIs.

Industry user projects may have high innovation and exploitation relevance but not necessarily equally so for scientific excellence, which is still the predominant criterion for TNA.

While industry users should bear the full costs of TNA since they do not provide open access to their often proprietary research results, this approach is not suitable for supporting SMEs as TNA users. For SMEs, TNA should help them generate exploitable research results, and they should not be expected to generate income for research infrastructures.

EU funding for TNA requires recipients to provide open access to the resulting data, which makes TNA less appealing to industry users. This limitation should be acknowledged, and it implies that industry will generally not be the primary users of TNA offered by RIs at the EU level. Instead, industry players often use national RI component facilities, which generates necessary revenue for these facilities. Some provider RIs face challenges in balancing the competing national/industry demand and the delivery of EU-funded TNA.

REA services mention that maintenance of paid-for TNA service modes can be beneficial for ensuring the availability of TNA services during periods when EU-funding is unavailable.

REA presents intriguing results from the survey on making TNA sustainable:

- Better integrate the TNA instrument with cluster research projects, Partnerships, and ERC grants.

- Allocate the TNA budget directly to ESFRI RIs/ERICs (allowing them to recruit TNA providers) or to other central TNA managing entities.
- Establish a central TNA scheme/project with harmonised TNA reimbursement, possibly partial reimbursement.
- Maintain a central TNA budget at EU level (e.g., RI, MSCA, etc.) instead of project level to allocate TNA flexibly when demanded.
- Encourage co-funding from national sources and seek contributions from non-EU Third Countries using TNA.
- Consider relieving the TNA budget from users' travel and subsistence costs, with these costs covered by home institutions or special national/EU budgets.
- Alternatively, allow for more users' travel and subsistence emphasizing TNA support largely as users' travel and subsistence support.
- Extend the duration of SERV projects to ensure continuous TNA provision and reduce set-up costs.
- Keep the programme unchanged except for reshaping the thematic scope of SERV calls.

The existing triangle Networking, TNA, and Joint Research, supported under H2020 IA and to some extent in HE SERV projects should continue. TNA has most impact when combined with networking and service development: networking activities foster collaborations and shape research to better align to EU priorities. Joint research on better services ensures RIs are fit for the future and provide best services and scientific support to TNA users.

Presentation from European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (EC DG RTD) on exploring a future framework for further integrated and sustained TNA access schemes: see respective slide presentation on a planned WP2025 CSA topic.

The audience question if national co-funding can be a feasible community approach to make TNA sustainable. They note that national co-funding might be available for some countries but not others, and that aiming at a possible contribution to access costs of only around 20% may be more realistic. However, the limited duration of the current HE co-funding scheme does not give enough time to set up appropriate governance and decision making bodies and rules, to be developed and agreed upon with Member States and other stakeholders, nor to identify thematic priorities and the best strategies to tackle them.

Another question concerns the type of access-related costs which should be co-financed. Some RIs require 100% EU funding for additional personnel efforts related to TNA or for travel costs of external TNA users. In contrast, national co-funding might be more feasible for other cost items for these RIs.

4.4 Session 4 - SERV projects' impact on policies & innovation

How is impact generated 'in practice', how to best highlight it?

What is the impact on International Cooperations, how to best tailor it?

What is the impact on innovation, how to best track it?

Views heard:

A central access portal would serve ideally also for collection and presentation of impact from SERV projects and TNA.

Policy briefs should not need to be produced by the projects, but in fact SERV projects would rather provide respective data to EC DG RTD/REA to extract the impact value.

TNA activity is a prime example of successful Science Diplomacy for policies, by promoting international collaboration on important policies (e.g. with respect to polar regions); this becomes visible through European RIs participating in large international initiatives.

A good way to raise visibility and impact is to align/link SERV project meetings to major EU policy meetings.

Challenge-driven SERV projects e.g. with a focus on global change/biodiversity, or on pandemics preparedness/response, are well involved with pertinent HE Partnerships, or missions, which indeed can be reported in policy briefs.

Other SERV projects supporting e.g. research on air traffic safety or the safety and resilience of building environments are immediately policy-relevant by generating important data to underpin respective EU regulations.

Some SERVs generate policy briefs by closely working with JRC where JRC has a mandate, with JRC also giving input to align the scope of TNA calls to identified EU policy needs.

REA inquires about RI contributions to international collaborations, including bilateral and regional collaborations, and the value of international collaboration-focussed DEV calls.

International cooperation is inherent to the activities of EU level RIs. Still, the specific EU request to include Ukraine was welcomed.

Most survey responses consider the 20% limit of TNA for users from Third Countries to be adequate. Some, however, find this limit too restrictive, in particular in cases where global research challenges such as e.g. pandemics or climate change are concerned. Common and sustained collaboration frameworks with RIs in Asia and the US could be useful.

EC DG RTD services note that if justified, it is possible in grant agreements to allocate more than 20% of TNA to users from Third Countries.

Others confirm the utility of the 20% threshold, as otherwise users from advanced, R&D intense countries like e.g. the US may outcompete EU researchers on the EU-funded TNA, without equal reciprocal use of respective Third Country facilities by Europeans.

EU's international policy objectives should be made clear, as in view of global politics and security concerns, countries like Russia and China should preferably be rather impeded in accessing European RI facilities.

Specifically on the question of what the impact on innovation is, and how best to track it:

SERV projects offering the EU's most advanced facilities for use would, 'by design', spread innovation across the EU, but it is unclear to what extent this comes from project partners' joint research, or from TNA user projects' results. Furthermore, it is unclear how such innovative outcomes can be highlighted.

It is acknowledged that industry-driven innovation would not be the main remit of EU-funded TNA in SERV projects.

EC services report that, while only 8% of the TNA users are directly industry-linked, many of the academic TNA users work on user projects that, in fact, are cooperations with industry; hence, industry does benefit from TNA indirectly through these cooperations with academia.

Research results from TNA-user projects and from beneficiaries' joint research, too, often become available only after the SERV project's end date. This makes it difficult to capture the resulting impact.

Some SERV projects have dedicated innovation committees that systematically identify and highlight exploitable outputs e.g. on industry fairs and exhibitions as part of the agreed activities under their project's work plan.

Challenge-driven SERV projects, e.g. addressing pandemics, should normally design and generate high impact and innovation outputs, but it is not clear, 'if', 'how', and 'to which extent' SERV targeted should continue to support innovative TNA-derived outputs in order to turn these into tangible and visible high impact.

The impact session was concluded by a flash presentation by a SERV project Coordinator who also manages a major national physics infrastructure in a Widening Country⁹. Challenging statements were tabled indicating focus on the excellence criterion alone may lead to reduced impact for specific challenges to be addressed, such as specific societal issues, or e.g. EU coherence, in terms of, e.g., young researchers from less advanced Widening Countries being less competitive with TNA proposals. Large infrastructures, with EU-funded TNA making up for only a small percentage of their total users group, may just select user proposals matching respective EU-requested challenges, thus in fact not triggering the intended extra research focussed on the identified challenge. Large SERV consortia may lead to 'access bubbles' populated by the larger 'excellence' community linked to a SERV project.

These statements were followed by a controversial debate, stating that SERV projects' TNA selection committees, comprising external evaluators, would impede the formation of perceived closed-shop 'access bubbles'. It was argued that excellence must, in any case, remain the prime criterion for choosing TNA projects.

Others shared the view that such 'access bubbles' may form, and that more incentives should be given to attract new TNA user projects that really match the SERV-targeted specific challenges, or target more specific users groups.

External expert reviewers of TNA-comprising projects, though being experts in the field of the project under review, are often not aware of the existence of this TNA-offering project in their field.

⁹ [Are we dealing with „access bubble“?, Michał Młynarczyk, TNA Workshop 2025.](#)

There is evidence that TNA selection panels rank proposals from newcomers sometimes lower. Dedicated training for potential early career users is advocated, and priority should be given in cases of ex-aequo-rated proposals. Additionally, twinning schemes are proposed to link proposers from Widening and EU15 countries. Another suggestion for good practice is that certain incentives can be offered if the group accepts a newcomer from the Widening Country.

TNA use counts when normalised to R&D personnel/country do not confirm underrepresentation of TNA users from Widening Countries, as seen on the slides shown in the TNA study conducted.

Better and wider advertising of TNA opportunities is needed, to reach the respectively targeted thematic, societal or geographical user communities, so as to enhance the impact of the TNA schemes.

TNA Workshop

Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures under Horizon Europe SERV projects

Experience from stakeholders and feedback to policy

Thursday, 30 January 2025
Auditorium SDR1 (Covent Garden 25th floor), Place Rogier 16,
Brussels

AGENDA

Meeting chaired by Andrea HUTTERER, REA, Head of Sector
Research Infrastructures

08:30 – 09:00	<i>Welcome Coffee</i>
09:00 – 09:20	Welcome, Introduction, Objectives Agnès ROBIN (EC DG Research and Innovation, Head of Sector for Open Science and Research Infrastructures) Sari VARTIAINEN-MATHIEU (REA, Head of Unit for Reforming European R&I and European Research Infrastructures)
09:20 – 09:40	Survey Results on SERV Projects and TNA Antonio VENTURA, REA, RIs
09:40 – 10:20	Presentations from 3 SERV Projects exemplifying common issues: CanSERV project , Manuela PAUSAN & Thomas STEGER, BBMRI ERIC EURO-LABS , Adam MAJ, IFJ PAN Kraków Infra4NextGen , Rory FITZGERALD, ESS ERIC
10:20 – 10:45	Points of view on TNA: ESFRI , Elena HOFFERT, Vice-Chair of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures – ESFRI TNA Study report , Audrey RICHARD, COO and Deputy Director of the European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents - ERINHA SERV community feedback , Barbara SCHRAMM, Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf- HZDr
10:45 – 11:15	<i>Coffee Break</i>
11:15 – 12:15	Session 1: TNA at the core of SERV projects
12:15 – 13:15	<i>Networking Lunch</i>
13:15 – 14:15	Session 2: Administrative challenges of TNA
14:15 – 15:45	Session 3: Sustainability of TNA
15:45 – 16:15	<i>Coffee Break</i>
16:15 – 17:00	Session 4: Policy dimension of SERV projects
17:00 – 17:30	Workshop take-home messages and future directions
17:30 – 17:30	Closure of Meeting

Participants list

Name	Organisation	INFRA SERV project
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HOLTEL Andreas	European Research Executive Agency - REA	
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FASANO Gelsomina	European Research Executive Agency - REA	

Acronyms list

EOSC - European Open Science Cloud

ERA - European Research Area

ERIC - European Research Infrastructure Consortium¹⁰

ESFRI - European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures¹¹

FP10 - upcoming 10th Framework Programme for Research & Innovation (2028-2034)

HPC - High Performance Computing

HE - Horizon Europe

IERO - International European Research Organisation

IA - Integrating Activities – predecessor to HE SERV in H2020's Research Infrastructures work programme

INFRA - The denomination of the Call Research Infrastructures in the Work Programme

INFRA-DEV – A destination in the HE Research Infrastructures Work Programme for “Developing, consolidating and optimising the European research infrastructures landscape, maintaining global leadership”

INFRA-EOSC - A destination in the HE Research Infrastructures Work Programme for “Enabling an operational, open and FAIR European Open Science Cloud ecosystem”

INFRA-SERV - A destination in the HE Research Infrastructures Work Programme for “RIs services to support health research, accelerate the green transition and the digital transformation, and advance frontier knowledge”

INFRA-TECH - A destination in the HE Research Infrastructures Work Programme for “Next generation of scientific instrumentation, tools and methods and advanced digital solutions”

INSTALLATION means a part or a service of a research infrastructure where TNA user projects are conducted; a research infrastructure consists of one or more installations.

JRC - Joint Research Center

MS - Member State

MSCA - Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

NCP - National Contact Points

REA – European Research Executive Agency

¹⁰ [European Research Infrastructure Consortium \(ERIC\)](#)

¹¹ [About | www.esfri.eu](#)

RI - Research Infrastructures - facilities, resources and services supporting users' research projects, they include research laboratories, scientific instrumentation and technologies, collections of data and materials, computational tools, and communication networks.

TNA - TransNational Access

ac-TNA means TNA costs reimbursed as actual costs

uc-TNA means TNA costs reimbursed as uncit costs

VA - Virtual Access

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